

CLIMATE CHANGE AND THE CHALLENGE OF DEVELOPMENT IN AFRICA – A NEO-MARXIAN PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

Climate change impacts various sectors, from agriculture to fashion. It affects farmers' yields, the productivity of wine tappers, and fishermen's catches. It disrupts weather patterns, influencing rainfall and sunshine availability critical for farming. Fashion designers face material scarcity due to climate effects. Climate change is exacerbated by capitalist greed, with the bourgeoisie causing it while the proletariat suffers its consequences, like ozone layer depletion.

This study provides a thorough examination of how climate change presents a significant obstacle to development in Africa. It suggests that climate change could hinder Africa's pursuit of meaningful and sustainable development, employing a qualitative analytical approach and drawing on system theory as a theoretical framework. It draws from the neo-Marxist perspective on climate change and asserts that climate change could persist as an ongoing existential challenge for humanity. Moreover, it suggests that it might exacerbate human cruelty towards one another, exacerbate disparities between the affluent and the impoverished, the ruling class and the working class, and widen the developmental gap between the world's affluent and impoverished regions unless societal stakeholders initiate a significant reset.

It is recommended that the best time to combat climate change is yesterday. The next-best time is today, which demands qualitative mitigation, through quality advocacy, capacity building, technology transfer, and adequate financing. We are quick to say that will be nearly impossible without the political will on the path of global leaders, the collaborative effort of global citizens, and friendly handshakes, between the countries in the northern and southern hemispheres.

Key Issues: Climate Change, Development, Africa, Marxism, System theory, Paris Agreement.

Introduction

The motivation for this study is hinged on how climate change exacerbates existing inequalities and exploitation within African societies. The prevailing notion is that these disparities and instances of exploitation are products of industrialized nations or countries situated in the Global North. Due to these inequalities and exploitation, the African region's strive for development is hampered. In recent years, the impact of climate change on Africa's efforts towards development has emerged as a prominent concern both within academics and among development experts. Surprisingly, however, there have been very few research works on the subject matter using the Marxian approach. This study is, therefore, geared to fill this lacuna.

Climate change affects everyone – the farmers in the villages, the wine tappers on the palm trees, the fishermen in the rivers, the fashion designers in the shops, the financial experts in the banking halls, the clubbers and club owners in the cities, the doctors in the hospitals, the lecturers and the researchers in ivory towers. Climate change impacts the accessibility of favourable weather patterns, like rainfall and sunlight, for farmers, consequently influencing the productivity of their farms. The number of kegs of wine that the wine tappers can sieve from the palm trees is determined by a good or bad climate. Dried or shallow rivers affect fish and fishermen's catch. Climate change influences the accessibility of cotton and fabric resources for fashion designers. The affordability and availability of papers and stationeries to the researchers and lecturers in tertiary institutions are to a large extent determined by climate change. To the clubbers and club owners, the prices of wines are determined by climate change, the same as the price of pepper soups. It affects the prices of household goods in supermarkets and the availability of grains, yam tubers, cassava flakes, corn flours, and meat in the markets.

Climate change influences various aspects of society, spanning politics, economics, and social interactions. It impacts urban development, life spans in both rural and urban settings, and even the selection of wines available at wine stores. It affects the prices of foodstuffs in the markets, the prices of litres of fuel at gas stations, and clothes in boutiques. The quality of life available to us as individuals and groups is constantly being threatened by climate change (See the Economist Report, 2022). We are all in it, yet the case of climate change is a case of one man's mess is another man's suffocation with bad odour. The bourgeoisie is primarily the cause, the proletariat are greatly the sufferers. The depletion of the ozone layers resulting in climate change is an offshoot of the bourgeoisies' greed and quest for materialism with little or no care for the environment.

Climate change arises from humanity's drive for wealth, the bourgeois drive for productivity and profit, unchecked expansionist tendencies, and strategies for power and materialism, all originating from the frameworks of capitalism, colonialism, neo-colonialism, and the appropriation of resources from the global south for the benefit of the global north.

“Man was born free and equal but everywhere he goes, he was in the chain,” asserted John Locke. At the outset, there existed neither wealth distinctions nor socio-economic disparities, no division between the affluent and the impoverished, no classification of nations into developed or developing, and no differentiation between first-world and third-world countries. In the beginning, the man was a man. What we have at best is the gender division. The disparities we have today are

not the creation of nature, but man's creation. Humans' inherent self-centeredness and pursuit of private gains at the expense of public gains brought us to where we are today. In Adam Smith's words: 'It is not from the benevolence of the butcher, or the baker, that we expect our dinner, but from regard to their self-interest' (Jahan and Mahmud, 2015).

Unfortunately, men's self-interest and greed are not equal. One man's self-contentment and fulfilment are another man's starting point. Same as groups, nations, and continents. Ancient men scattered on Earth moved from survival and self-preservation to social groupings and communal subjugation of their perceived hostile groups and communities. This was a period in history in which 'every man was against every man' such that life was 'nasty, brutish, and short. '. Communal wars, intertribal wars, and later nations and continental wars became commonplace (Hobbes, 1651; Locke, 1947). The fights and wars back then were initially for territory (land – the primary factor of production) conquests. As communal, tribe, national, and continental wars increased, men began to take fellow men as 'spoils of wars – prisoners of wars' with the hope of using them for individual and communal services on farmlands leading to the second epoch of man's pursuit of self-interests rooted in serfs, servitudes, and 'slavocracy'. Based on the fact that the slaves were given a small portion of what they produced for consumption purposes, excess production became a common experience. Within communities, some men appropriate more slaves to themselves, while others do not get them at all. This was made possible because men were built differently and may sometimes command more wisdom than one another based on the exertion of their mental capacity. This brought about surplus produce, called capital by the bourgeoisie, as exemplified by capitalism, which in itself is a product of feudalism (Karl Marx, 1867).

More capital means greater wealth for capitalists. While formal slavery subsided through the growth of civilization and was later officially called off by the global authority (the League of Nations and the United Nations Charter), man's inhumanity to humanity continues through the exploitation of the proletariat by the bourgeoisie within village settings, communities, towns, cities, nations, and the global stage in the form of capitalism – entrepreneurship, colonialism, and neo-colonialism. This is what led to the incorporation of Africa – its nationalities and people – into the world economic order rooted in capitalism and its variants of colonialism and now neo-colonialism. This is because man's quest to conquer the world and inherently others continues unabated until today. Good examples include the ongoing war between Russia and Ukraine, Israel, and Palestine, with several lives lost and valuables destroyed.

As Claude Ake (1981:14) rightly stated:

The integration of Africa into the world capitalist system by Western colonialism and imperialism is the event which has had the most influence in shaping the economic and political development of contemporary Africa.

Our perspective aligns with that of certain academics both within and beyond the African continent that Africa's backwardness is not entirely of its people making but of a deliberate usurpation and exploitation of its natural and human resources by the global north in the form of imperialism – colonialism and neo-colonialism. Climate change is directly linked to the increasing challenges

swiftly spreading across the continent. This is caused by Western industrial emissions and the greenhouse effect. The continuous exploration of African mineral resources such as gold, diamond, and other precious metals for the benefit of Western countries is arguably responsible for most of the conflicts going on in Congo, Sudan, Libya, and Egypt. Armed struggles, terrorism, and communal clashes in most African nations like Nigeria, Niger, Mali, and Burkina Faso have been linked to the countries from the global north. However, this does not entirely exonerate Africans from being part and parcel of those who are making the Earth less livable, as some of the African bourgeoisie are partners in crime (Ake, 1981).

Arguably, climate change is a by-product of capitalism and some of the existential problems faced by Africa and Africans today can be attributed to climate change – from insecurity (arising from armed robbery to social unrest – communal clashes, farmers/herders clashes that have now metamorphosed into banditry, kidnapping, and terrorism); to excruciating poverty among the populace, and growing socio-political and economic inequality, and the problem of development as a whole. While noting that some of these problems were not today's problems or entirely caused by climate change, we are of the view that climate change is further compounding their existence and implications for development in Africa.

We, therefore, reject the notion that Africa is poor because Africa is poor, which in itself is a circular reason argument. It is equally absurd to presume that Africa is backwards because of defective institutions or inferior mentality and virtues. Just as the notion that Africa cannot develop without external funding and intervention like loans, grants, and aid which in most cases have further impoverished the countries in Africa. The assumption that without external funding and intervention, Africans cannot mitigate the adverse effect of climate change may in itself be a misnomer.

In contrast to industrialized nations, less developed countries face heightened vulnerability to climate change due to their limited ability to adapt and their heavy reliance on natural resources for sustenance. Roberts and Parks (2006) contend that developing nations experience a dual injustice: they bear the brunt of environmental damage and climate shifts, while also being pressured to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions, which may hinder their economic progress (Huang and He, 2012). Climate change therefore no doubt poses an existential threat to Africa's growth and development.

Methodology

This study employs a descriptive case study design. The study uses secondary data sourced from various official documents, journals, reports from government and non-governmental organizations, newspapers, and the Internet. The data collected were content-analyzed.

Literature Review and Conceptual Clarifications

Climate change means different things to different people. The way a pastoralist in the Sahara desert whose livestock's lives are threatened by the absence of vegetation due to low or dearth of rainfall may likely be different from a man in the Niger Delta coastal region whose means of livelihood have been wiped out due to oil pollution, and therefore unable to engage in fishing. In the same vein, a farmer from the South Western Nigeria who is faced with changes in climate change due to variations in the period of rainfall and harmattan may equally have a different opinion from the people of Russia who are faced with 'climate change adverse effects, which include more floods, windstorms, heat waves, forest fires, and the melting of permafrost' (Kyte, 2014). It is these differences in experiences and social context that made the definition and explanation of phenomena in Social Sciences and Political Science in particular problematic endeavours. This no doubt accounts for the multiplicity of definitions and the reason there is hardly a consensus on what a concept means.

In simple terms, weather refers to the immediate atmospheric state of a location at a specific time, whereas climate pertains to the long-term patterns and shifts in weather conditions experienced in a particular area over time. Weather comes in the form of rainfall and sunshine, fog and snow, cold and hot temperatures. Hakim and Patoux (2021) defined weather as the state of the atmosphere in a specific place and moment. It encompasses the various elements of the atmosphere such as temperature, humidity, wind speed, and precipitation. The characteristics of weather can change rapidly and fluctuate across short periods ranging from minutes to days. Weather refers to short-term atmospheric conditions, while climate encompasses the extended, varying patterns of weather over decades, centuries, and beyond (Hakim and Patoux, 2021). Classical climatology offers a systematic categorization and explanation of the diverse climate patterns present across the globe. Climate conditions differ across regions due to factors such as latitude, proximity to oceans, vegetation cover, the presence of mountains, and other geographical elements (Ahlonso, Ding, and Schimel, 2017). Moreover, climate undergoes temporal fluctuations, ranging from seasonal shifts to longer-term changes cutting across years, decades, or even epochs like the Ice Ages. Changes in the average climate conditions or their variability that endure for significant periods, decades or more, are termed "climate change" (Ahlonso, Ding, and Schimel, 2017).

Climate change therefore can be said to be sudden and adverse change in the weather and climatic conditions of a place arising from unwholesome human activities to the environment. Climate change, as described by the Framework Convention on Climate Change (FCCC), is "a change of climate that is attributed directly or indirectly to human activity, that alters the composition of the global atmosphere, and that is in addition to natural climate variability over comparable periods" (Pielke, 2004). It refers to the enduring change in temperature and usual atmospheric conditions within a particular location (Encyclopedia Dictionary, n.d). Climate change refers to a change in the usual weather patterns and conditions. The current acceleration in climate change is predominantly driven by human activities, such as the use of fossil fuels like oil, gas, and coal in various sectors such as homes, industries, and transportation. When these fuels are burned, they emit greenhouse gases, primarily carbon dioxide (CO₂), which traps the Sun's heat and leads to a rise in global temperatures. Presently, the Earth is approximately 1.1 degrees Celsius warmer than

it was in the 19th century, with a corresponding increase of 50% in atmospheric CO₂ levels (BBC, 2022). This definition and explanation of climate change are quite instructive and explanatory. It captures not only what climate change is, but also the factors that are responsible for climate change and also recognizes the role of human factors in climate change. The definition is however too generic or simplistic as it tends to liken all changes in climatic conditions to climate change which is not the case.

The United Nations (2022a) defined climate change as ‘long-term shifts in temperatures and weather patterns. These shifts may be natural, such as through variations in the solar cycle. But since the 1800s, human activities have been the main driver of climate change, primarily due to burning fossil fuels like coal, oil, and gas.’ This is because ‘Burning fossil fuels generates greenhouse gas emissions that act like a blanket wrapped around the Earth, trapping the sun’s heat and raising temperatures. Examples of greenhouse gas emissions that are causing climate change include carbon dioxide and methane. These come from using gasoline for driving a car or coal for heating a building, for example. Clearing land and forests can also release carbon dioxide. Landfills for garbage are a major source of methane emissions. Energy, industry, transport, buildings, agriculture, and land use are among the main emitters.’ (Ibid)

Thus, we can conclude that climate change refers to a variation or change in the atmosphere and weather conditions of a geographical entity over a long period of time, caused by humans’ deliberate or accidental unwholesome activities on the planet with Mother Earth being the major hit. At the heart of climate change are energy generation and consumption. It is in this regard, that the United Nations posited that “generating electricity and heat by burning fossil fuels – coal, oil, or gas – causes a large chunk of the greenhouse gases, such as carbon dioxide and nitrous oxide that blanket the Earth and trap the sun’s heat.” (United Nations, 2022b). From villages to towns, towns to cities man needs the energy to survive even though the bulk of energy consumed and its effect are from the cities. According to the UN-Habitat, urban areas play a significant role in exacerbating climate change. Approximately 80% of energy consumption and over 60% of greenhouse gas emissions are attributed to cities, despite covering less than 2% of the Earth’s surface. Alarmingly, cities bear the brunt of the consequences of climate change (Ibid).

What the foregoing suggests is that climate change is no respecter of persons and places, and thus can affect the lives and means of livelihood of the vast proportion of humanity. Besides the fact that greenhouse emissions and other toxic substances released into the atmosphere pose a direct threat to mankind, the fact is many people are likely to die of climate change due to its nefarious effects on the ecosystem. This is because climate change affects people’s ability to engage in farming, fishing, and providing pasturage for animals, breathing in quality air, and has resulted in the displacement of people and natural organisms from their natural environment.

As earlier noted, man is a selfish being who is always preoccupied with his gain at the expense of others. Man in search of livelihood and pursuit of economic activities, engages in toxic activities that have made the world less livable for others and indirectly for himself. Through deforestation, bush burnings, animal hunting, discharge of wastes into water bodies, the release of carbon monoxide from generating sets, vehicles, industrial machines, etcetera; the ozone layers have become depleted resulting in unpredictable global weather and climate across geographical areas.

The world's ecosystem is imperilled because of man's greed and selfishness. The air we breathe is polluted. The waters we drink are poisoned. Rainfall is irregular. The scorching sun envelopes the earth. Green vegetation is becoming non-existence. Wild and domestic animals are becoming extinct. Man's lifespan has become shortened. The entire earth may become extinct sooner than expected without a reset button, all thanks to climate change.

Man's quest for improved material well-being is becoming a myriad. Development may soon become a taboo for humanity. Climate change may perhaps be man's greatest enemy since the dawn of civilization as it has affected the quality of life socially, politically, and economically. Through climate change and as earlier posited: man's access to quality foods, water, shelter, and clothing at affordable and fair prices has greatly impinged. Thus, while the world seems to be growing in terms of technological advancement, and in several regards, humanity seems to be retrogressing as far as sustainable development is concerned. The question is what is development before we speak of sustainable development?

Development Explained

There is an avalanche of authors, scholars, and views on the subject of development, such that attempting to explain the concept may appear a sheer waste of time. However, for scholastic exercise and operationalization of concept, we must make an effort to provide a contextual prognosis; otherwise, it may be apt to say – that development is what development is, and of course which will be tantamount to an imbecilic regurgitation. Certainly, it would be an understatement to suggest that the concept of 'development' has not been contentious and subject to change throughout history. As Thomas (2000: 1) contends, development is “contested ... complex, ambiguous.” Gore (2000: 794–5) notes that in the 1950s and 1960s a “vision of the liberation of people and peoples’ dominated, based on ‘structural transformation.” This perception has tended to ‘slip from view’ for many contributors to the development literature. A second perspective is a definition embraced by international development donor agencies that Thomas (2000) notes. This is a definition of development that is directly related to the achievement of poverty reduction and the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) (and maybe the Sustainable Development Goals now). (Andy Sumner & Michael Tribe, 2006 – addition mine). The author further stated that ‘there is a third perspective from a group of writers that Hickey and Mohan (2003:38) broadly identify as ‘post-modernists’. The ‘post-modern’ position is that ‘development’ is a ‘discourse’ (a set of ideas) that shapes and frames ‘reality’ and power relations.’

In effect, we can deduce that the concept of development has evolved– there was a phase when development was perceived as liberation from political, social, and economic bondage. That is the reason Amartya Sen cited in Ninalowo (2007), defines development as freedom. Next to this, is the era when development was perceived as being equal to material wealth (how much of material assets an individual or nation has), and there is the stage in which development is seen as connoting to a man or society state of spiritual or cultural well-being. To this effect, Merriam-Webster Dictionary defines development as ‘the act, process, or result of developing, the state of being developed.’ It describes it as a tract of land that has been made available or usable: a developed

tract of land.’ The question what does it mean to be ‘developing or developed.’ To be developing means to be growing, while to be developed in this context means to ‘have grown’, but is it all growth that is tantamount to development? We do not think so. It is in this regard, that we equally found it hard to accept the definition provided by the Collins Dictionary that says, ‘development is the growth of something such as a business or an industry.’ Or the one provided by the Cambridge Dictionary which defines development as “the process in which someone or something grows or changes and becomes more advanced” (Cambridge Dictionary, 2022).

Expanding upon the concept of development, Seers (1969) proposes that although opinions may vary on what constitutes development, there should be a consensus that the ultimate goal of development is to create circumstances conducive to unleashing the full potential of human personality, a goal that should be universally embraced. Discussion of development is incomplete without addressing the essential prerequisites, namely: access to basic necessities such as food, engagement in various forms of occupation including education, agricultural work, or homemaking, emphasis on equality as a primary goal, involvement in governance processes, affiliation with a genuinely economically and politically autonomous nation, and attainment of satisfactory educational standards, particularly literacy (Shah, 2017). What a definition! Development is not just about growth but about the totality of man as far as access to basic needs of life is concerned and a sense of justice, freedom, and equality among other members of society. Development is about the quality of life available to an individual or group of people politically, economically, and socially. It is about having a healthy life and living in a free and just environment according to the above explanation. This foregoing view is similar to the one provided by the Pallipedia Dictionary which defined development ‘as the process of providing the conditions that offer opportunities for improving the quality of human life in a community. According to it, development normally covers three aspects of change’, namely:

1. It tries to raise people's living standards, including improvements in food, housing, education, employment, sanitation, environmental protection, and health services.
2. It tries to create conditions that can increase growth in self-esteem through improving or introducing social, political, and economic systems and institutions that promote human dignity and respect.
3. It tries to increase people's freedom to choose by increasing the range of available goods and services, travel, and social and political contact and by decentralizing government decision-making, to achieve greater local participation” (Pallipedia Dictionary, 2022).

Impliedly, we can say development represents positive or ‘good change’, but that immediately raises a philosophical and ethical question about what is good and what is bad. If a county authority constructed a beautiful road in a locality resulting in a free flow of traffic but also increasing the number of deaths by accidents in the area, can we say the construction of the road is good or bad? Apart from the fact that some people believe that there is nothing good or bad but that ‘goodness’ is relative and subjective as what is good to ‘A’ may be bad to be ‘B’. For instance, a ban on the

importation of rice grains may be perceived by farmers as a ‘good policy’ capable of bringing about increased homegrown rice and profitability of farmers; but to the importers of such items, the policy may be seen as a ‘bad policy’ because the policy is certainly going to affect their social, economic and even political life of the importers of such grains. To a fisherman who goes to the river and catches plenty fishes, to him, his effort has yielded ‘good results’, but to the generality of the society, he is contributing to adverse climate change effects. This is also true of a hunter who killed a lion in his hunting game. Perhaps, a question may need to be raised and answered as to what constitutes ‘general good’. To whose benefits is the immediate and ultimate mitigation of climate change for instance? Can supposedly ‘good development’ be pursued without adverse effects on climate and humanity as a whole?

Sumner and Tribe (2008:10) posited that “a common theme within most definitions is that ‘development’ encompasses ‘change’ in a variety of aspects of the human condition. Indeed, one of the simplest definitions of ‘development’ is probably Chambers’ (2004: iii, 2–3) notion of ‘good change’, although this raises all sorts of questions about what is ‘good’ and what sort of ‘change’ matters (as Chambers acknowledges), about the role of values, and whether ‘bad change’ is also viewed as a form of development.” The definition of "good change" is subject to debate since there is not a single, universally accepted answer. Perspectives held by certain segments of the development community might not align with those of other groups within the community or society at large (Kanbur, 2006, as cited in Sumner and Tribe, 2008). Indeed, development holds diverse interpretations for different individuals and groups. For someone whose primary concern is securing sustenance for themselves and their family, development may primarily signify the availability of food, crucial for averting hunger and ensuring survival. In such a context, the significance of infrastructure may pale in comparison. This dynamic potentially elucidates the phenomena observed in developing nations, wherein public infrastructures like rail tracks and train coaches are subject to theft, and constructed roads are marred by the deliberate creation of potholes by citizens. These actions, though seemingly counterintuitive, reflect the desperate measures taken by individuals to address immediate, pressing needs amidst the broader context of underdevelopment.

Three main perspectives on the definition of development have emerged over the years (Sumner and Tribe, 2008). Firstly, development is seen as a gradual, long-term process leading to fundamental societal changes, such as transitioning from rural or agricultural societies to urban or industrial ones. Secondly, development is viewed as achieving specific, desirable targets within a shorter to medium-term timeframe. Lastly, development is seen as a prevailing discourse rooted in Western modernity. In the first perspective, development entails significant shifts in societal structures, impacting various dimensions including economic, social, and technological aspects. This involves changes in socio-economic structures such as ownership, production organization, technology, institutional frameworks, and legal systems.

During the colonial era, for instance, there was a massive disruption of traditional societies. Virtually, all aspects of African traditional societies and people’s lives were disrupted – the political institutions were superimposed with elected or appointed leaders who nurtured little or no reference to the traditional values. Economically, many abled men and women from Africa

were mass exported to Europe for forced labour, the introduction of white and blue-collar jobs affected the African agrarian economy which was mostly rooted in communalism as most young men travelled to cities in search of these jobs. This dealt a devastating blow to the communal nature of African societies. Socially, many of the African cultures and religions were described as barbaric, archaic, and inconceivable for human practice resulting in communal fights among community members. There were social, economic, and political changes in the existing traditional social, economic, and political structures. A move from monarchism to democracy is seen as 'political growth'. Africa's migration from a subsistent agricultural economy to an import-dependent economy due to an obsession with manufactured products whose raw materials are either stolen or deceptively cornered from Africa is tantamount to development. The embrace of Christianity and Islam without moral values such as the social, political, and economic elites continuing to milk the poor dried through wanton embezzlement of public resources is modernity. Unfortunately, such transition is what the West regards as development as exemplified by the Bretton Wood institutions.

To the Bretton Wood Institutions and other international development experts and agencies, development is seen 'as a short to the medium-term outcome of desirable targets.' This kind of development is prescriptive and targets-driven. It comes in the form of various IMF, World Bank, and other development partners' conditionalities to developing and third-world countries. Like a medical doctor or a pharmacist will say to a patient, take this pill (policy/policies), and get relief from your headache (developmental problems of unemployment, poverty, huge national debt, poor exchange rate, etc.). The workability of such development policy prescriptions by many developing countries that have followed this path has been called into question, as many of them seem to have moved from 'frying pan to fire' based on available facts and statistics though some will argue, that the failure of such policies can be adduced to poor implementation and institutional failure. During the Asian financial crisis of 1997, Thailand served as a prime example where the government adhered to the International Monetary Fund's recommendations, including raising interest rates, implementing severe austerity measures, and initiating a liberalization program. These actions ultimately resulted in the collapse of Thailand's economy. To lend credence to this is the aftermath of the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) by President Ibrahim Badamosi Babangida's regime which some scholars have opined that it is partly responsible for the present economic woes facing the Nigeria State. (See Stiglitz, 2002).

It is the failure of the development experts, agencies, and practitioners as demonstrated above in most countries that brought about the third school of thought on development. The third definition paradigm of development sees development 'as a dominant 'discourse' of Western modernity. This school of thought on development 'is based on the view that development has consisted of 'bad' change and 'bad' outcomes through the imposition of Western ethnocentric notions of development upon the Third World. This is the 'post-modern' conceptualization of development (one might also refer to this as the 'post-development', 'post-colonial' or 'post-structuralist' position' (Sumner and Tribe, 2008:14). To the scholars of the above school of thought, the notion that many developing countries including African countries are not developing due to institutional failure, lack of modern practices, and inferior intelligence of the people of these countries are not true, rather, the backwardness of Africa and many developing countries are traceable to their

incorporation into unequalled western capitalism relationship brought about by deliberate improvisation and exploitation of these countries through imperialism manifestly through colonialism and neo-colonialism. Thus, and according to Sumner & Tribe (2008:14),

“Development is a label for plunder and violence, a mechanism of triage (Alvares, 1992: 1). Poverty is a myth, a construct, and the invention of a particular civilization (Rahnema, 1997: 158). Culturally perceived poverty need not be real material poverty: subsistence economies which serve basic needs through self-provisioning are not poor in the sense of being deprived. Yet the ideology of development declares them so (Shiva, 1988: 10), *and even developing countries like Nigeria, Ghana, and Thailand among others are poor or backward today, their poorness or backwardness is not of their own making but of deliberate usurpation of their potential (material and immaterial) for the benefit of the global north. In essence, ‘development has been a mechanism for the production and management of the Third World... .. organizing the production of truth about the Third World... .. Development colonized reality, it became reality’ (Ibid).*

Arguably, there are three fundamental schools of thought on development, namely:

1. The Structuralist/Classical Approach: sees development as a gradual social change and transformation that takes place over a long period, bringing about a holistic change in the mode of production and social relation of production, for instance, from agricultural production to industrial production. It also affects the way and where people live – from rural communities to urbanization and cities. This is rooted in the classical political economists like Adam Smith, David Ricardo, and Marxian tradition as propounded by Karl Marx and Engel among others. To this school of thought, a society cannot progress nor develop without a conscious and rational effort to transform the mode of production and social relations of production. Subsistent farming for instance must give way to mass production and specialization. To this school of thought, development either happens when the market is given freehand (‘the invisible hands of demand and supply) bringing about economic prosperity in the long run, or there is a deliberately planned effort to move a society through a planned command economy to achieve socio-political and economic prosperity for all.
2. The Modernization theorists – development as being characterized by certain features such as a high level of infrastructure, employment, absence of poverty, high level of literacy, societal equality, social justice, and increased per capita income, among others. Thus, the global society can be classified into two – the global north with these basic characteristics, and the global south lacking these basic features and values. The variance of this school of thought is that there is a marked difference between people in developed countries and those who live in developing countries. The people in developed countries are superior in terms of intelligence, capabilities, and skills compared to the people in developing countries. It is in this regard, that the writings of Rowstow’s theory of modernization –

development, and underdevelopment are somewhat relevant; and the policies and prescriptions of Western development agencies, Bretton Wood Financial Institutions, and most International Development experts find an explanation. These scholars argue that ‘through increased investment, increased exposure to modernized, Western society, and changes in traditional culture and values, societies will become more highly developed’ (Jacob, 2017).

3. The Radical / Post-modern Approach is of the view that the classification of nations and people into developed and undeveloped are mere labels, and laden with value judgment, lacking any objective sense and more importantly as a mechanism for managing countries in the global south. In this perspective, “the idea of development stands today like a ruin in the intellectual landscape. Its shadow obscures our vision... .. Delusions and disappointment, failures and crimes have been steady companions of development and they tell a common story: it did not work... .. But above all, the hopes and desires that made the ideas fly, are now exhausted: development has grown obsolete.” (Sachs, 1992: 1 cited in Sumner and Tribe, 2008:15).

The fact and perhaps the truth is that man’s quest for development – a better way of living has nefarious effects on the planets and the earth seems to be the worst hit. Capitalism compared to other economic mechanisms like socialism, communalism, and communism emphasized individualism as against collectivism. It emphasizes individual wealth ahead of collective wealth. It promotes competition without reference to equity and this uncensored quest to outwit others by individual and juridical persons has devastating consequences on the world ecosystem. It is instructive to note that neither the global south nor the global north is immune from the effect of climate change but developing countries and African countries appear to be in ‘double jeopardy.’ To unravel this jeopardy and the threat it poses to African development necessitated the adoption of system theory as our tool of analysis.

Theoretical Framework

The disparity that exists between the ‘core’ and ‘periphery’ and semi-periphery countries (apologies to Immanuel Wallenstein) in terms of modernization and development is either an illusion or caused by the forceful incorporation of these countries into the world’s unequal capitalist relations of production perpetuated through imperialism – colonialism, and neo-colonialism, and to worsen this situation is the further threat posed by climate change on African countries quest for development. This argument becomes more valid if we consider the whole world as a unit of existence (a system comprising several subsystems).

The world, like the human body, is a single entity with several parts, and their interworking and efficient functioning make a whole system. Systems Analysis was influenced by Austrian-Canadian biologist Ludwig von Bertalanffy and American sociologist Talcott Parsons (1902–79). The central idea of systems analysis is based on an analogy with biology, just as the heart, lungs, and blood function as a whole, as do the components of social and political systems. When one

component changes or is under stress, the other components adjust to compensate for it (Britannica, 2022).

Concerning the international plane and international relations, American political scientist Morton Kaplan delineated types of international systems and their logical consequences in *System and Process in International Politics* (1957). According to Kaplan, for example, the Cold War rivalry between the United States and the Soviet Union created a bipolar international system that governed many of the two countries' foreign and security policies. Locked in a zero-sum game (when one country wins, the other loses), the two superpowers watched each other vigilantly, eager for gains but also wary of the threat of nuclear war" (Ibid). At the moment, the world is a multipolar system with strong national players like China, the USA, Russia, and France.

Essentially, the system analysis or approach to socio-political and economic behaviour is of the view that every system exists alongside other systems – no system exists in isolation, and that what affects one system has the possibility of having an impact on another system. For instance, within a country, local politics is a reflection of regional politics, whereas the latter is a reflection of national politics. Development at one level of government most likely affects development at other levels of government. Within the global context, global politics is a reflection of geopolitics, happening on the international scene has a way of rubbing off on happenings in some other countries. In this regard, The 1944 International Labour Organization (ILO) Declaration of Philadelphia states that "poverty anywhere is a threat to prosperity everywhere;" and war/crises anywhere is a threat to peace everywhere (ILO, 2019).

Corollary, the debilitating effects of climate change are a threat to human survival. The Russia – Ukraine War resulted in the scarcity of wheat and grains in the world, with a concomitant increase in the prices of bread worldwide. For instance, the price of a family-size loaf of bread before the outset of the war in Nigeria in 2021 was 300 naira, as in October 2023 this year, it now costs as much as one thousand two hundred naira. The same is true for the prices of foodstuffs such as rice and other staple foods. A bag of rice in 2021 is less than thirty thousand Naira; at present, it is sold as much as fifty thousand Naira. There are serious implications for unwholesome human activities on Earth in both developed and developing countries.

Climate Change and Its Implications for Africa Development

The dreadful impact of global warming caused by 'the presence of water vapour, carbon dioxide, methane, and certain other gases in the air,' arising from industrial pollution, deforestation, overpopulation, pollution, and burning of fossil fuels in cities and villages is a threat to man's continuous existence everywhere and anywhere. "*Climate change is one of the greatest threats to humanity. The entire foundation of good health is in jeopardy with increasingly severe climatic events. In Africa, frequent floods, waterborne, and vector-borne diseases are deepening health crises. Although the continent contributes the least to global warming, it bears the full consequences,*" said Dr Matshidiso Moeti, WHO Regional Director for Africa.

According to the African Development Bank Group (2019),

Africa is the most vulnerable continent to climate change impacts under all climate scenarios above 1.5 degrees Celsius. Despite having contributed the least to global warming and having the lowest emissions, Africa faces exponential collateral damage, posing systemic risks to its economies, infrastructure investments, water and food systems, public health, agriculture, and livelihoods, threatening to undo its modest development gains and slip into higher levels of extreme poverty.

This view was equally shared by the Wilson Centre. According to them, “About a third of countries in East Asia and the Pacific, Latin America and the Caribbean, South Asia, and sub-Saharan Africa face elevated risks from extreme weather—such as floods, storms, and droughts—and from macroeconomic, debt, and banking-sector risks. These cascading risks will further compound existing vulnerabilities, further weakening countries’ abilities to confront climate impacts” (Pazarbasioglu, 2020). Like the rest of the world, climate change affects all Africans and virtually all endeavours of life.

1. Health Implication

Several global health reports have shown that more Africans stand the risk of death from water-borne diseases due to a lack of access to portable drinkable water. For example, the World Health Organization stated that in Africa, 40% of health emergencies related to climate were attributed to water-borne diseases over the last twenty years. Furthermore, the organization highlighted that diarrhoea ranks as the third most significant cause of illness and mortality among children under the age of five in the region. It is instructive to note that many of these fatalities could be avoided with access to clean drinking water, proper sanitation, and good hygiene practices. The study also revealed that diseases transmitted by vectors, such as yellow fever, constituted 28% of health crises related to climate change, with zoonotic diseases like Congo-Crimean hemorrhagic fever being the third most common. This fever, transmitted by ticks and livestock, has a mortality rate of up to 40% during outbreaks (WHO, 2021).

2. Social Implication

Since 2010, there has been a significant increase in occurrences of natural disasters like heavy rainfall and flooding. Between 2017 and 2021, a striking 70% of all-natural disasters took place. Among these, floods were the most common, constituting 33% of reported incidents and leading to the displacement of numerous families (WHO, 2021; BBC, 2022; Oguntola, 2022). In West Africa and North Africa, flooding and drought are commonplace. In Nigeria for instance, several states were submerged in water due to flooding for several weeks. Specifically, from Lokoja in Kogi state to Yenagoa in Bayelsa, Bayelsa to Anambra, Anambra to Jigawa ... such that 33 out of the 36 states of the federation were flooded largely due to discharge water from the Lagdo Dam resulting in the death of 603, injuring of over two thousand people, damaged of 82,035 houses, and destruction of 332,327 hectares of land and 1.3 million persons displaced from their communities. Many displaced families now live in different Internally Displaced Camps (IDPs), while some families have had to send their loved ones to relative places. Some husbands have travelled from their ancestral places to foreign places in search of greener pastures for themselves and their families (WHO, 2021; BBC, 2022; Oguntola, 2022).

3. Food Scarcity

Constant flooding in countries like Nigeria has rendered a lot of farmers jobless and caused a reduction in agricultural produce. Countries like Somalia and other North African states experiencing droughts for decades have been faced with acute food shortages. In this vein, 360 Africa.org - a Non-Governmental Organization with a focus on climate change posited thus:

“...the effects of climate change are already being felt by people across Africa. Evidence shows that the temperature change has affected the health, livelihoods, *food productivity*, water availability, and overall security of the African people, such that ...seven of the ten countries most at risk from climate change are in Africa. Africa has seen a decrease in rainfall over large parts of the Sahel and Southern Africa, and an increase in parts of Central Africa. Over the past 25 years, the number of weather-related disasters, such as floods and droughts, has doubled, *resulting in Africa having a higher mortality rate from droughts than any other region*” (Emphasis added).

The prices of foodstuffs, staple foods, and grains are daily on the increase. Food inflation rates in Africa are on the increase like never before. In Algeria, it is 10.3%, Angola is 24.5%, Botswana is 5.9%, Egypt is 47.9%, Ghana is 27.1%, Sierra Leone is 57.21, Nigeria is 35.41%, and Zimbabwe is 60.3% (Trading Economics, 2024). The implication of the foregoing is that many families cannot afford three square meals per day, and those who can afford them hardly comply with the demand for balanced diets.

4. Economic Implication

The means of livelihood of many Africans have been adversely affected by climate change. The United Nations University specifically stated that ‘climate change will negatively impact Africa's growth and development prospects, particularly in the absence of adaptation and mitigation. Losses of up to 4% of Africa's gross domestic product (GDP) are projected, and agriculture is a major economic impact channel given the high share of Africa's GDP accounted for by rain-fed agriculture’ (United Nations University World Institute for Development, 2022). Therefore, the question is not whether climate change will affect Africa and Africans, the question is to what degree is it affecting Africa, and what solutions exist for these self-induced and externally aggravated problems. As pointed out earlier, “climate change will undoubtedly present one of the most significant risks to Africa’s sustainable development objectives over the next decade, and nowhere is the threat more imminent than on its coastlines. This is because, more than 30 million Africans live within the flood hazard zone around the Atlantic and Indian Oceans, out of which 2 million are likely to be flooded each year. Abidjan is a case in point: It is ranked among the world’s top 20 cities in terms of population exposure to floods, and its asset exposure is similarly high at \$42 billion” (Mbaye, 2022).

5. Security Implication

At the root of most insecurities in Africa is climate change. The exacerbating cases of kidnappings, the reoccurring incidence of farmers/herders clashes in sub-Saharan Africa, the rising militant groups, and social and communal conflicts are on the increase due to climate change. Due to climate change, green vegetation is becoming non-existence, and the constant fight between farmers and pastoralists who want to feed their herds are familiar experience. Communities that have lived peacefully together for ages are now at loggerheads for farmlands and water.

Unfortunately, some of the arms and weapons being used by the militants and groups are illegally smuggled and procured from developed countries. Some keen observers have even argued that the Western world has continued to cause and sponsor conflicts in African countries to continue to perpetrate the illegal mining and exploration of mineral and natural resources without ethical consideration of the debilitating effect on their host communities where such resources are domiciled.

6. Political Implication

In 2010, Mohamed Bouzizi – a vendor of fruits and vegetables from Tunisia who immolated himself in the town of Sidi Bouzid. kick-started civil uprising that almost brought the entire Arab world to its knees in a popular movement which has been tagged the Arab Spring because of the rising cost of bread and other food items. Bouzizi's act of self-immolation not only symbolized the beginning of the Arab Spring, which resulted in the removal of President Zine El Abidine Ben Ali, the demise of Moammar Gadhafi, and the forced departure of Hosni Mubarak from office in disgrace.

Georgetown Security Studies Review (2023) reported thus:

With seven coups since 2020, West Africa is drawing global attention as a hotspot for conflict and a critical locus of discourse on climate security. Rising temperatures and scarce rainfall have amplified the dangerous effects of weak governance, ethnic rivalries, lack of economic opportunities, and violent extremism in the region. Government policy failures in the region have accentuated inequalities that worsen the effects of climate change. The recent spate of coups indicates a deepening governance and security crisis in the Sahel. This political instability makes it difficult for West African countries to respond to increasing violence and humanitarian crises amplified by a changing environment. With the effects of climate change growing more acute, West African governments must improve their practices and capacities. West Africa depends on agriculture for nearly 50% of its economic activity, making the region sensitive to interactions between the physical effects of climate change and existing social, economic, and political vulnerabilities. Africa has less arable land than any other region, and its limited agricultural capacity is becoming increasingly scarce due to rising temperatures and decreased rainfall.

Africa indeed faces double jeopardy and the threat from climate change such that billions of Africans stand the risk of food insecurity, homelessness, displacement from ancestral communities, political upheaval, and loss of means of livelihood. Billions of Africa may lack access to potable water, millions of farmers and fishermen may soon be rendered jobless due to climate change, and millions of children stand the risk of mortality due to preventable diseases like cholera. People who live in the cities may soon lose access to clean air and a habitable environment. The danger is severe, the risk is huge. It is time for inclusive action that will save humanity and Africans.

Inclusive Climate Change Action: a Catalyst for Sustainable Development in Africa

Considering the calamitous implication of climate change on Africa's survival and development, African leaders and Africans, in general, must rise to stem this dangerous trend through wholesome and friendly interaction with the environment, but much more, the world must rise to save itself and Africa in particular from this "growing pains."

According to Okonjo-Nweala (2022), findings from the New Climate Economy indicate that taking decisive action on climate change could result in global economic gains of at least \$26 trillion by 2030. Moreover, it could create over 65 million new jobs in low-carbon sectors by the same year, an amount equivalent to the total workforce of both the United Kingdom and Egypt combined. Also, such action could prevent more than 700,000 premature deaths caused by air pollution compared to the current scenario. In addition, it is also projected to generate approximately \$2.8 trillion in government revenues by 2030 solely through reforms in subsidies and the implementation of carbon pricing. She expounded further:

If fairness was the only goal, the impetus to act would lie solely with developed economies. Make no mistake, the big emitters absolutely must step up their domestic climate action, and quickly. But building the new climate economy is also a once-in-a-lifetime opportunity that every African nation should prioritize and claim a stake in." She further stated elsewhere that "whether driven by opportunism or a sense of moral justice, the world's developed and emerging economies must take action at home and help Africa deliver the investments that will bring the goals of the Paris Agreement within reach.

The Paris Agreement

Speaking of the Paris Agreement, the truth is that nearly all the countries in the agreement, especially the developed countries have failed to abide by the spirits and letters to the pact in this agreement, rather, they have over the years paid lip service, and on some occasions backed out of the agreement. Like most International treaties, the global north especially the Super Powers has the superior context to further disempower the global south countries, though the Agreement is supposed to be an internationally enforceable agreement on climate change which was ratified by 196 nations during COP 21 in Paris on December 12, 2015, and became effective on November 4, 2016. By early 2017, 195 countries had signed it, with only Nicaragua and Syria abstaining. The objective is to restrict the increase in global temperatures to well below 2 degrees Celsius, ideally

aiming for 1.5 degrees Celsius above pre-industrial levels. This aim emerged in response to the failure of the 1997 Kyoto Protocol Agreement, which faltered after President George W. Bush withdrew the United States' signature and declined to submit it to Congress for ratification. Instead, Congress enacted the Byrd–Hagel amendment, mandating that any future U.S. participation in climate accords must be accompanied by comparable commitments from developing nations. Similarly, the Paris Agreement encountered a setback when President Trump announced the U.S.'s withdrawal in June 2017.

In essence, the Paris Agreement was created to enhance and supplant the Kyoto Protocol, a previous international pact aimed at limiting the emission of greenhouse gases. It came into effect on November 4, 2016, and has been endorsed by 195 nations and officially approved by 196 as of January 2021. (Britannica, 2022). To realize its ultimate temperature objective, nations aspire to peak global greenhouse gas emissions at the earliest possible juncture, striving for a carbon-neutral world by the middle of this century. Notably, the Paris Agreement represents a significant milestone in the global endeavour to address climate change, as it marks the first time a legally binding accord unites all countries in a collective endeavour to pursue ambitious actions to combat climate change and adapt to its impacts (Wagner and Allan, 2020).

Despite a rocky start and an initially lacklustre implementation, the Paris Agreement stands as one of the most ambitious moves by global leaders to tackle climate change. COP27 serves as evidence of this determination. According to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) (2022), COP27 yielded a significant breakthrough by securing funding for "loss and damage" incurred by vulnerable nations due to climate-related disasters. Simon Stiell, Executive Secretary of UN Climate Change, expressed enthusiastic satisfaction with the outcome of COP27, particularly highlighting the commitment of developed nations to the 'loss and damage fund'. In his words:

This outcome moves us forward. We have determined a way forward on a decades-long conversation on funding for loss and damage – deliberating over how we address the impacts on communities whose lives and livelihoods have been ruined by the very worst impacts of climate change (UNCC, November 20, 2022).

This view was equally shared by Aberg (2022) when she opined that ‘COP27 will go down in history as the UN climate change conference where the Loss and Damage fund was agreed. After decades of pushing, this is a momentous victory for climate-vulnerable developing countries;’ but is mere availability of funds a sufficient condition for mitigating climate change? Combating climate change requires a moral and financial commitment by all member countries and global citizens. It requires political will. This is because executing the Paris Agreement demands socio-economic transformation, based on the best available science and practices. It is meant to ‘works on a 5-year cycle of increasingly ambitious climate action carried out by countries. By 2020, countries submit their plans for climate action known as nationally determined contributions (NDCs).’ Also, there is a requirement for the transfer of climate-resilient technology from developed nations to developing ones, along with the necessity for capacity building. Strategies

aimed at combating climate change must encompass both immediate and prolonged actions (UNCC, 2022).

Broadly speaking, climate change actions include: “cutting emissions, adapting to climate impacts, and financing required adjustments.” As earlier stated, the Paris Agreement remains the most ambitious attempt for humanity to combat climate change, while some level of progress has been made especially concerning the ‘loss and damage fund’ agreement through COP27, the facts remain that so much needs to be done. This is because “switching energy systems from fossil fuels to renewables like solar or wind will reduce the emissions driving climate change. But we have to start right now. While a growing coalition of countries is committing to net zero emissions by 2050, about half of emissions cuts must be in place by 2030 to keep warming below 1.5°C. Fossil fuel production must decline by roughly 6 per cent per year between 2020 and 2030” (UNCC, 2022)

Conclusion and Recommendations

The best time to implement the pact in the Paris Agreement was yesterday, the next best time is today. That means, all hands must be on deck to save our lovely planet from the greenhouse effect and impending doom of climate change. Besides the ‘loss and damage fund’ agreed upon at COP27, concrete efforts must be made by global leaders to promote and ensure food sufficiency across the bipolar world of the global north and the global south.

There is a need for more qualitative advocacy campaigns across the nooks and crannies of the world. Such campaigns must draw a connection between people’s continuous present and future survival. It must be communicated in the local languages from city to city, town to town, and village to village. It must be stated as a death and life issue. This is because climate change is mostly caused by individual activities, such as using firewood to cook but which impact is collectively borne by all.

Tree planting must be encouraged and galvanized to a new level in cities and local communities. While we may not be able to address the mistakes of the past, the fact is that we can address the challenges of the present, while helping to mitigate against future challenges.

Although it is beneficial to pursue development and modernization, it's crucial to emphasize that these endeavours should be carried out sustainably. Genuine and sustainable development ensures that the current generation's needs are met without jeopardizing the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (United Nations, 1987).

Certainly, African nations have expressed ambitious goals to develop economies that are resilient to climate change and have low carbon emissions in their Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) to the Paris Agreement. However, a significant portion of these pledges rely on receiving sufficient financial, technical, and capacity-building assistance (AfDB, 2023). Our view however

is that even though African countries like many other developing countries have the moral right to demand compensation for being the hardest hit as far as the effect of climate change is concerned. The continent's leaders must act decisively and cooperatively to take the destiny of the continent into their hands without necessary waiting cap-in-hands to get peanuts from the developed countries, which may further impoverish the continent as development aid hardly comes without conditions that are meant to promote the interest of the donors. The continent has the huge potential to rise above all its present and anticipated future challenges.

Some of the measures required to combat climate change in Africa and the world over include: “creating the conditions for the phase-out of coal and rapid scale-up of renewables in the energy sector; investing in shared, electric, and low-carbon transport in cities; scaling up sustainable food and land use systems, including forest landscape restoration; targeting investment to resilient water infrastructure; and reducing emissions from key industrial value chains, such as plastic” (Okonjo-Nweala, 2022).

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